

The Likely Irreversible Catastrophe of Global Warming and Human Ignorance

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Overview

The temperature on this planet is rising and has now reached 1.2 degrees Celsius. A 1.2 °C increase means that the amount of heat on our planet will increase, and if it is not controlled, it will continue to increase. If things continue as they are, there will be nothing that can be done. Despite this, people are unaware of the problem, despite hearing about it. As a result, they continue to aggravate the situation. Furthermore, there are many environmental activists who campaign to prevent global warming and its dangers, but they, like African elites and International Relations educators, may need knowledge and further ideas about the increase in global warming. As a result, the goal of this article is to answer three questions that will help these critical people, other readers, and officials in the Horn of Africa who are working to prevent global warming: What is global warming, and how does it contribute to climate change? Why is the global warming rising? What can be done to change this? This article will also shed some light on the political debate surrounding this subject.

Introduction

Prior to 1992, the majority of people were unaware of rising temperatures or global warming, let alone its consequences. However, during that year, when the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), or, in short, the Earth Summit was held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, the UN addressed this issue for the first time and issued the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). This agreement, which aims to prevent human threats to the environment in order to control global warming, went into effect on March 21, 1994 (UN 2015). It is now an international agreement that was signed in 198 countries (UN 2022).

However, on June 1, 2017, President Donald Trump of the United States announced that his country would withdraw from the Paris Agreement, and the Trump administration did not participate in the Paris Agreement (PA) the following year (Leggett 2019, 1). The entire world was taken aback by this matter (Sharma 2017, 4). Because the United States is a great power, the world's political leader, and known for leading academics and science, and

because the United States claims to stand for global development, this matter has taken the entire world by surprise. The Horn of Africa was one of those surprised by Trump's action.

As a result, the purpose of this article is to raise awareness among the people of the Horn of Africa and the rest of the world about the importance of mitigating global warming. It will present four points: understanding what global warming is and what it entails or may result from; its cause; how to control it; and convincing the public that it is important not to look at this topic politically or that politicising it is wrong. Finally, this last section will discuss the implications of President Trump's withdrawal from the Paris Agreement..

Climate Change

The world we live in today is in grave danger, which we are not fully aware of (Unitarian Universalist 2006). The UN Secretary-General, Antonio Guterres, is one of the well-known figures who has witnessed the disaster of global warming. He stated during a speech to the World Economic Forum in Davos that global warming is putting the world in danger and that oil companies should be held accountable for their role in causing this danger (Cottasova 2023). The first elements of this threat, namely climate change, are already present. River floods have increased; seas have frozen and others have melted; the rainy season has changed; and new diseases have emerged and are spreading (Centre for Biology Diversity). The most dangerous thing that can end the life of the entire world, which is the topic we will discuss here, is the increase in global warming, which causes the things we mentioned above (Centre for Biology Diversity).

The global temperature is rising; it has risen by 1.2 or 1.5 degrees Celsius since the pre-industrial era (Abnett 2021). According to research conducted by the world's

environmental experts, this issue is destructive and will have a negative impact on global life (IPCC 2022). Everyone is normally aware of the dangers of rising temperatures. As we all learned in primary school, water boils at 100 °C (the boiling point) and freezes at 0 °C (the freezing point). As a result, a person with knowledge

can understand that the world's temperature is rising, posing a threat to human life, plants, and animals.

Today's actual global temperature is within the known range. The average temperature is 15 °C, with the highest at 71 °C and the lowest at -89 °C (Space 2022). If the world's temperature continues to rise, it indicates that the world is getting closer to danger. As a result, it has been confirmed that the planet's temperature is continuing to rise.

The World Health Organization has confirmed that the amount of global temperature that has increased in the last ten years of the twenty-first century (2008-2017) is greater than it was in the last 100 years of the nineteenth century (NASA 2017). Finally, it was agreed that there is no doubt that the global climate is warming, and that if this trend continues, the world will be turned upside down. This must not be known only by those who have studied science or astronomy; additionally, as a political scientist and social scientist, it is important to understand and ask what is causing the increase in global warming and how it can be avoided. When something changes, common sense and knowledge tell us that we should look into why. Scientist G.S. Callendar stated in 1938 that the amount of CO₂ emitted by factories causes the "greenhouse gas effect," which causes global warming, and that fossil fuels are the primary source of CO₂ emissions (Wear 2022).

The most productive and populous countries emit the most CO₂. China emits 32% of CO₂, followed by the United States (12%), India (8%), Russia (4%), and Japan (3%), for a total of 55% of CO₂ emissions. Plant deforestation and decay also contribute to CO₂ emissions (World Population Review 2023). Electricity and heat production (25%), industry (21%), agriculture, forestry, and other land uses (24%), transportation (14%), and others (10%) are the sectors that emit the most CO₂ into the atmosphere (EPA, 2017). This is an issue that must be addressed. Stop reading and consider the significance of the aforementioned sectors emitting CO₂ that contributes to global warming to our lives. Approximately 95% of them are resources that we rely heavily on.

The Evolution of Global Warming

There is also an intriguing issue. The molecules that make up the earth's atmosphere and keep the planet's temperature stable are the same ones that cause global warming. Scientists discovered in the nineteenth century that the world's temperature was rising due to the "Greenhouse Effect," which was caused by molecules of natural gases Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and Methane. CO₂ and NO₂ are the two most influential gases in the atmosphere to keep the global warming stable, on the other hand. This seemed to the people unbelievable. Another surprise was that when this issue first emerged in the 17th century, the scientists who spoke about it were regarded as insane (Wear).

Scientist Svante Arrhenius added to what we've said by claiming that industries that were appealing and saw rapid progress would cause the world's temperature to rise, but other scientists disagreed. G.S. Callendar, another scientist, entered the debate in 1938, claiming that the amount of CO₂ emitted by factories into the atmosphere is the only factor that can cause the "greenhouse effect," which causes the climate to warm. While most people around the world did not believe the reports, in 1950, researchers came out and agreed that the climate was warming. This inspired D.C. Keeling, a scientist, to develop a temperature measurement. At that point, many academics became interested in learning more about this long-debated climate issue. Finally, it was discovered that the scientists' predictions had been correct (Weart).

Temperature increase

So the pertinent question is, "How does the temperature rise occur?" Some people believe that as the sun heats up or becomes hotter, the earth's temperature rises. The sun is normally very hot and does not heat up, but it is not to blame for our planet's rising temperatures (NASA 2020). It is very far away from Earth, roughly the same distance as the Moon is from the Sun (149.6 million km) (Royal Mesums Greenwich 2018). The sun provides the same amount of heat energy to both the earth and the moon, but our planet and the moon are not the same temperature (Kazmeyer 2018). The temperature of the moon when the sun shines is 100 degrees Celsius, and it is -173 degrees Celsius at night (Space 2012). The highest temperature on Earth is 55 degrees Celsius, while the lowest temperature is -89 degrees Celsius (Space 2022). This is because the sun's heat rays do not directly reach the earth; if they did, life on our planet would be impossible.

The "atmosphere," which is a layer that surrounds the earth and keeps radiation, long rays of the sun, and particles out, is necessary for life to exist on the planet. Only the sun's short rays can reach the earth through this atmosphere. There are billions of molecules of gases in the atmosphere, including Nitrogen (N₂) 78%, Oxygen (O₂) 21%, Argon (Ar) 1%, Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) 0.038%, NO₂, Water Vapor (HO₂) 0-4%, and Methane (CH₄), as well as up to three others that are not very important but useful, such as Sulfur dioxide (SO₂), Ozone (O₃), and [Nitrogen (N), Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), Nitrous oxide (N₂O)]. It would be uninhabitable if the atmosphere did not exist (USGS 2011).

These molecules are responsible for achieving "radiation equilibrium," which means balancing the amount of radiation or short-wave hot energy (solar radiation) transferred from the sun to the earth with the volume of long-wave radiation (long wave radiation) returned

from the earth to the atmosphere. They allow a specific quantity of light radiation to pass through to the earth. The earth then emits what are known as long-wave radiation waves. When the earth emits long radiation waves, the atmosphere's job is to absorb them and send them out into space (USGS 2011). As a result, the earth's temperature remains stable, allowing life to flourish.

However, 10% of the radiation escapes and travels above the atmosphere. The remaining 90% is absorbed by the atmosphere. Then, to maintain the balance (radiation equilibrium), they disperse 50% of the energy (warmth) from the radiation they absorb to the outside of the atmosphere and return the other 50% to the earth (Weart 2017). It is also worth noting that the most active molecules that do this work are those with the smallest number in the molecules that make up the atmosphere, which are CO₂ (0.038%), HO₂ (0-4%), and CH₄. These molecules are in charge of absorbing the radiation emitted by the earth while also maintaining equilibrium radiation (USGS 2011).

As a result, if the earth emits radiation other than its natural and the sun's natural radiation, the radiation that leaves the earth and enters the atmosphere is greater than usual. This means that the earth's natural radiation has been supplemented with non-natural radiation. The atmosphere absorbs it and then sends half of it to space while returning the rest to the earth, causing the natural radiation from the atmosphere plus half of the additional man-made radiation emitted by the earth to always return to the earth. This system is summed up in two words: "greenhouse gas effect." As a result of the greenhouse gas effect, the earth's temperature rises. The question is, where does the man-made radiation that the earth emits into the atmosphere come from? Is there anything that can be done about it? (Macmillan 2016). And we will go over it in detail in the following sections of the article.

Nevertheless, let's first see what will happen if the global warming increase persists. According to NASA's Earth Observatory (National Aeronautics and Space Administration), increasing global warming has a negative impact. It has the following consequences: Climate change and its consequences will worsen in the coming years. Cold places will continue to move into warmer climates, and warm places will move into colder climates; river floods will increase; seas will continue to freeze, and others that have frozen and are now melting will continue to melt; the changed rainy season will persist and have unanticipated negative consequences; and new diseases will emerge and spread (Biology Diversity). In addition, coastal erosion will worsen and sea levels will rise (Earth Observatory 2017). And these warning signs have already begun.

Consider how often you've heard about a drought and its effects on people. Drought does not only affect Africa. It occurs even in the United States, but it is invisible because their support is strong. Massive floods have killed and displaced people and animals in countries such as Pakistan, India, and others. We hear and see on television about hurricanes in many parts of the world, including the United States, and even name them, such as Katrina (LA/MS/FL/GA/AL) in 2005, which killed 1200-2000 people and cost the US \$ 108 billion, and Sandy in 2012, which killed 285 people and cost the US \$74.1 billion (Pflanzer 2016).

The weather will not be the same as it once was, but it has changed. Temperatures will rise, with more hot seasons and fewer cold seasons. The sea level will rise, and communicable and noncommunicable diseases caused by the climate change. It should be noted that the sea level data collected came from different seasons. The average annual rise in sea level was 1.7mm; the total annual rise was 22mm, 0.7 feet, or 8.7 inches. Between 1993 and 2009, it increased by 3mm, or 0.16f, or 1.89 inches per year, for a total of 48mm.

If current trends continue, sea levels will rise to 0.59 m or 1.9 f in 2099, despite the fact that only 10% of the world's population lives on land above sea level. Global ice melt is the primary cause of sea level rise. Malaria, as well as other communicable and non-communicable diseases, will become more prevalent. Floods and rains will cause more damage in terms of life and property (Earth Observatory 2017).

These gases that humans emit into the atmosphere, according to health experts, not only cause the climate to warm but are also hazardous to human health. In short, they disrupt

the body's respiratory and circulatory systems. If we recall its importance in biology, it has an important job, such as circulating the body with oxygen (oxygen) and removing CO₂ from it; providing nourishment to the body; removing waste or extra that are not needed so that the body can continue its work properly (excretory); protecting

the body from diseases; forming a clot when the body is injured, and so on. Furthermore, the gases emitted by factories are harmful to the urinary system, nervous system, and other organs (Kampa 2008).

Finally, as a scientist, G.S. Callendar stated in 1938 that the volume of CO₂ that factories emit into the atmosphere is the cause of the "greenhouse effect," which causes the climate to warm (Weart). Fossil fuels are the primary source of CO₂ emissions (EPE 2017). According to NASA's Earth Observatory website, increasing global warming has a negative impact on the climate, the environment, human health, and the economy (Pflanzer 2016). That is sufficient evidence that CO₂ has great negative effects on the climate.

Dealing with Global Warming:

Global warming (GW) is a matter of life and death for humans. According to the World Food Programme's 2018 annual report and as Andrew writes, the world hunger programme is slow

and hampered by a number of factors, the most significant of which is rising global temperatures (Andrew 2022). According to a UN report, the number of hungry people reached 828 million in 2021 and is rapidly increasing year after year, with an increase of approximately 46 million since 2020 and 150 million since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic (WHO 2022). Furthermore, as the World Bank reports (World Bank 2022), "Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, and Southeast Asia are home to roughly 80% of the global population most vulnerable to crop failures and hunger as a result of climate change, where

farming families are disproportionately poor and vulnerable." That is evidence of the perilous nature of global warming.

When it comes to food, Africa is the worst affected by global climate change caused by rising temperatures. Agriculture production in Africa, for example, has fallen by 35%, far more than in other parts of the world. The Horn of Africa, which used to receive rain four out of every five years, now receives rain three out of every five years. Food shortages are expected to affect half of Somalia's population by 2022. (US Embassy, 2022). Despite this, the global warming agreement continues to face political interference and pressure.

The issue of dealing with global warming was well received in 1992, when world countries UN Framework Convention on Climate Change Countries (UNFCCC) signed an

agreement with the code COP21 aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions that countries emit into the atmosphere, leading to an increase in global warming. It was followed by CMP-11, the Kyoto Protocol of 1997. It is also worth noting that the United States did not accept these agreements until the Paris agreement was signed at COP21/COP11 in 2015 (Nov. 30-Dec. 12), at which point the Obama administration became one of the 200 countries to ratify the agreement (UN 2015).

It was agreed in that agreement to reduce the quantity of pollution emitted into the atmosphere. The US agreed to reduce CO₂ emissions by 28%. However, the countries that ratified the agreement were surprised and shocked when US President Donald Trump

announced his country's withdrawal from the agreement on June 1, 2017 (Congressional Research Service, 2019). Countries that wanted to do something about this issue were relieved on July 7-8, 2017, when the 20 leading industrial countries reaffirmed the continuation of the global warming control agreement at a conference in Hamburg, in which Trump did not participate, and it was a setback for the US as 19 other countries reaffirmed the

continuation of the global warming control agreement (Andrew 2018). While implementing their Climate and Energy Action Plan (CEAP), the G19 countries reaffirmed their commitment to limiting global warming to 1.5 degrees Celsius or 2 degrees Fahrenheit, as stipulated in Article 2 of the Paris Agreement (Nathan Hultman 2018).

According to NASA (Kate 2021), the global temperature has risen by 1.5 degrees Celsius since the Industrial Revolution. So, the answer to the question of how to deal with rising global temperatures is simple: we emit CO₂ into the atmosphere, which causes the temperature to rise. Fossil fuels are the primary source of CO₂ emissions (Kate 2021), and there are five sectors that use fuel, each of which emits a certain number of CO₂ (EPE 2017). So the answer is simple: if we stop emitting CO₂ into the atmosphere, the temperature will remain constant at 1.5 degrees Celsius/2 degrees Fahrenheit. It is also good news that the world has options for dealing with it because it has reached a point where something can be done. According to Prof. Corinne Le Quere of the University of East Anglia and Geleta, if

nothing is done today, it will reach +6 °C by the end of the century (Geleta 2022, 2). Nothing, according to scientists, can prevent it from reaching that level.

Despite this, there are important questions that arise, such as, firstly, how it must be compatible with reducing the use of fossil fuels and the vision of the international community to eradicate poverty and hunger in the world through increasing employment. To eradicate poverty and hunger, one of the most important things to focus on is easy access to energy. As you can see above, the electric power sector is the biggest emitter of CO₂, which causes global warming. Climate change is the first priority that the G19 countries (G19 = G20-US) want to address according to the G20 climate and energy action plan of 2017 (G20 Information Center). The second question arises, namely, how can we overcome the fear of business that can lead to abandoning a method that has been the backbone of production for a long time and switching to another? And the third question is: who pays for the cost of these shifts from using fuel to another method?

In conclusion, it was agreed that the world must adopt the idea of "a strong economy and a healthy planet" (European Council 2017). It is encouraged to move from today's electricity generation method of using fossil fuels, which is the biggest sector emitting CO₂ to the atmosphere, to other sustainable methods of producing clean energy using energy efficiency, based on the implementation of reducing atmospheric emissions (an energy system with low greenhouse gas emissions).

Bottom line: GW is caused by CO₂ emissions. And CO₂ comes from fossil fuels, so we have to move away from using fossil fuels. Finding that solution is a win. But the problem is how to implement it. This debate requires further examination in a separate, more comprehensive article. However, we will summarise here the things we can do to change the use of fuel by the global community to stop or reduce CO₂ emissions. In the short term, we have two options: first, we can reduce our reliance on industrial products. People should stop overbuying the same commodity. For example, a person must not buy a new watch, phone, TV, laptop, or desktop until the ones on his hand break or get older. We should also conserve electricity by using low-energy light bulbs and turning off electrical appliances when not in use. The second method is to use alternative forms of energy generation.

Hydropower, wind power, solar energy, biomass, marine power, geothermal power, and nuclear power are all methods for generating energy. And it is dependent on what each country is capable of doing. Finally, it is the responsibility of every government and every individual to contribute to halting global warming.

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